

Contributions of Instructional Leadership and Teachers' Empowerment towards Achieving an Effective School System

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Abstract

This study examines the contributions of instructional leadership and teachers' empowerment towards achieving an effective school system. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population consisted of 2361 secondary school teachers serving in the 158 government owned public secondary schools in Zamfara State, from which 266 teachers were sampled through multistage random sampling technique using Cochran's sample size determination formula. Three structured questionnaires were adapted as instruments for data collection, viz; Instructional Leadership Questionnaire developed by Akram et al. (2017), the reliability of the instrument was computed based on the pilot testing and yielded the value of ($\alpha=.82$); School Participants' Empowerment Scale (SPES) developed by Short and Rinehart (1992) with Cronbach's alpha value of reliability .910; and School Effectiveness Questionnaire developed by Lezzote and Snyder (2011) with Cronbach's value of reliability .949. The data collected were analysed using both descriptive statistical method (Mean and Standard Deviation) and inferential statistical method (Pearson product moment correlation coefficient and standard multiple regression). The findings of the study revealed that, there is a significant high correlation between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness. The study also observed that both instructional leadership and teacher empowerment contribute significantly towards achieving effective school system with statistical values of ($\beta=0.515$, $t=11.000$, $p=0.000$); ($\beta=0.369$, $t=7.881$, $p=0.000$) respectively. Based on these findings, the paper recommends that, educational authorities, policy makers, school principals, classroom teachers should synergically cooperate together in the proper implementation and improvement of instructional leadership and teacher empowerment for the attainment of an effective school system.

Keywords: Instructional Leadership, Teachers' Empowerment, School Effectiveness, Contribution

Introduction

Education is the bedrock of any nations' socio-economic, cultural, religious and political development (Ikegbusi & Iheanacho, 2016). Educational institutions must be properly administered and managed in order to produce vibrant outputs that will contribute effectively towards national development (Oyededeji, 2012). In Nigeria, education is compulsory and a right of every Nigerian irrespective of

gender, social status, religion, colour, ethnic background and any peculiar individual challenges; and education is to be qualitative, comprehensive functional and relevant to the needs of the society (FGN, 2014). Instructional leadership puts teaching and learning in the school as a priority in order to improve the attainment of school's goals and missions (Botha, 2011). Instructional leadership encompasses those actions that the principal

takes or delegates to others, to promote teaching-learning outcomes (Dinie, 2017). On the other hand, Sparks (2003) stressed that, teachers are individuals that are important in leading changes to create an effective school system. Teachers are the critical actors in any education system. They are the public face of education, and their direct actions influence school characteristics such as curriculum implementation, execution of the established policies on education, students' academic achievements, effective school management, and maintenance of the schools' infrastructural facilities, among others (Crosswell, 2006). Not only has their classroom practice come under scrutiny but teachers are also now involved to a larger extent in school management and decision-making (Beare, 2001). According to Olorunfemi (2008), teachers are the backbone of the entire education system. Their effectiveness is perhaps the most important factor affecting the future development of education process (Ikegbusi & Iheanacho, 2016). In spite of the significance of instructional leadership and teacher empowerment towards the actualisation of school effectiveness, prior empirical studies expressed that, there have been some unsolicited factors affecting the process of achieving school effectiveness. Furthermore, related existing literature were critically analysed and thus found that, a number of research works were conducted on the relationship that exists between instructional leadership and school effectiveness as well as teacher empowerment and school effectiveness. However, there is a little or no existing literature that were conducted to examine the contributions of instructional leadership, teacher empowerment towards school effectiveness. The main objective of the current study therefore attempts to fill this literature gap by examining the level of contributions of instructional leadership, teacher empowerment towards achieving an effective school system.

Leadership means involving all stakeholders cooperatively in mutual learning and development for enhancing teaching and learning in schools (Khan et al., 2020; Lima, 2006). Comprehensively, instructional leadership refers to the direction, resources, and support provided by principals to the teachers and students to enhance teaching and learning (Tan, 2012; Rossouw, 1990). Leadership plays an important role in any organisation and educational institutions are no exceptions in this regard (Khan et al., 2020). Instructional leadership is directing and influencing the teachers for improving and practicing the school curriculum and helps to improve and achieve objectives of the school (Cotton, 2004; Murphy, 1988). According to Harris (2011) the most important factor in the success of the schools is the quality of leadership of the head teacher. The operative notion is that the quality of teaching and learning is largely dependent upon an individual or group that exercises supervisory responsibility for the core business of schools; namely, curriculum, teaching and learning (Fullan, 2020; Dinie et al., 2017).

Bolin (1989) described empowerment as teachers' investment with participation right and willpower to judge for what and how to teach in accordance of school policies and goals. The empowerment of employees serves as a significant factor in the success of the schools, businesses, or other organizations in which people are working toward a common goal. Teacher empowerment and teachers' sense of empowerment represent important variables in comprehensive school improvement efforts of today's effective schools movement (Sharp, 2009). Short & Rinehart (1992) posited that, school effectiveness/improvement is dependent upon increased opportunities for staff to participate in the decision making process in vital areas within an organization. Short (1994) stressed that, teacher empowerment is a process whereby

participants develop the competence to take charge of their own growth, resolve their own problems, and believe they have the skills and knowledge to act on a situation and improve it. Short and Rinehart (1992) also, viewed teachers' empowerment as the second name of participative or shared decision leadership. Teacher empowerment is an effort to increase professional responsibility of teachers in school (Muhammad, 2014). Teacher empowerment is enabled in a school setting that operates a democratic organisational climate. Policies and programmes related to teacher empowerment at different levels have great impact on the level of teacher motivation leading to speedy realization of the objectives of the school effectiveness (Lucey & Hill-Clarke, 2008). Furthermore, Teacher empowerment is a concept used to describe the process by which a professional educator can increase his/her enthusiasm, effectiveness and skills when it comes to the implementation of the established school goals. An empowered teacher appreciates his/her role as an educator and feels that the job she/he does has real value (Chhangte & Hnamte, 2020). Thus, it can be deduced that empowerment of teachers entails giving teachers all they needs which can be psychological, social-cultural or economical so as to make them fully commit to their various jobs (Jafar et al., 2021). Teachers' empowerment guarantees the effective performance of teachers' jobs through involvement in decisions (Squire-Kelly, 2012).

Generally, an organisation can be characterized as effective if it have attained a high point of goal attainment. The greater the goals are achieved the more effective is the organization (Zamir, 2020). According to Scheerens (2004), School effectiveness refers to aspects of teaching, learning, motivation and community involvement. In relating this view to the school, school effectiveness can be assumed as the capacity of a school to accomplish its goals (Mielcarek et al., 2005). School

effectiveness is influenced by communication in decision-making which is capable to change internal and external schools (Zamir, 2020). A school with such attributes that which consistently adheres to achieve its goals of establishment is referred (Scheerens, 2000). There are different models of school effectiveness aimed at explaining and determining what makes schools effective (Burusic et al., 2016). Several correlates of effective schools have been proposed (Burusic et al., 2016; Kirk & Jones, 2004; Lezotte, 1991) including: clear school mission developed in agreement between and shared by the principal and the teachers; high expectations shared by the school staff that students can succeed and that teachers can help them succeed; effective instructional leaders who reinforce the school mission and vision; students are provided with opportunity and time to learn, and teachers have clear expectations regarding what to teach and adequate time to teach; the school environment is safe and orderly, and cooperation and respect is stimulated; positive home-school relations are fostered, and parental involvement in school is stimulated; and student progress is frequently monitored and the results are used to improve their performance.

Objectives of the Study

The current study aimed at achieving the following objectives:

1. To assess the relationships between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness.
2. To assess the contributions of instructional leadership and teacher empowerment towards achieving school effectiveness.

Hypotheses

1. There is a no significant relationship between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness.
2. Instructional leadership and teacher empowerment do not contribute towards achieving school effectiveness.

Methodology

The population of the study consisted of all the serving teachers in government owned secondary schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria. There are 2361 teachers serving in 158 secondary schools across the state (Zamfara State Government, 2021). Cochran's formula (2007) was used to determine the sample size. The total sample in the current study distributed is 266 teachers all over the state. Multistage random sampling was employed in the selection of respondents due to the fact that all the teachers possess the same characteristics in the context of the current study. In order to achieve the objectives of this study, three instruments were adapted to measure the variables of the research, the instruments are: Instructional Leadership Questionnaire developed by Akram et al. (2017) was employed to measure instructional leadership practices and its features. It is a five Likert type scale consisting of 15 items. The reliability of the instrument was computed based on pilot testing method and yielded the value of ($\alpha = .82$) which denotes a high reliability of the instrument. In order to measure teacher empowerment and its features, School Participants' Empowerment Scale (SPES)

developed by Short and Rinehart (1992) with 13 Items was employed. The instrument has the Cronbach's alpha value of reliability of .910. For school effectiveness, Lezzote and Snyder (2011) five Likert type scale instrument with 21 items was employed. The instrument composite reliability was computed using Cronbach's alpha method and obtained the value of .949. Therefore, the instrument for data collection of this study consisted 49 items/constructs.

Furthermore all the three instruments adopted were found culture free thus, considered acceptable in the conduct of the current study. Data analysis was made through descriptive statistics using mean and standard deviation as well as inferential statistics using Pearson Correlation. The strength of the relationship was analyzed using Cohen (1988). The range of the interpretation of the relationship is illustrated below:

$r = -0.10$ to -0.29 and $+0.10$ to 0.29 is rated as Low correlation;

$r = -0.30$ to -0.49 and $+0.3$ to $+0.49$ is rated as Medium correlation;

$r = -0.50$ to -1.00 and $+0.50$ to $+1.00$ is rated as High correlation.

Results

Hypothesis 1:

There is a no significant relationship between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between School Effectiveness and other Variables

Variable	Mean	SD	Y	X ₁	X ₂	P
Y (School Effectiveness)	3.68	0.15	1			.000
X ₁ (Instructional Leadership)	3.68	0.08	.735**	1		.000
X ₂ (Teacher Empowerment)	3.95	0.07	.676**	.595**	1	.000

**Correlation is significant at the level of $P < 0.01$ (2-tailed).

The Pearson product moment correlation coefficient analysis of table 1 presented above revealed that, there is a high significant correlation between instructional leadership, teachers' empowerment and school effectiveness among public secondary schools of Zamfara State, Nigeria. School

effectiveness correlates with instructional leadership at the value of ($r = 0.735$; $p < 0.01$); while it correlates with teachers' empowerment at the value of ($r = 0.676$; $p < 0.01$). Instructional leadership however, correlates with school effectiveness at the value of ($r = 0.735$; $p < 0.01$); while it correlates with teachers' empowerment at

the value of ($r=0.595$; $p<0.01$). Furthermore, teacher empowerment correlates with school effectiveness at the value of ($r=0.676$; $p<0.01$); while correlates with instructional leadership at the value of ($r=0.595$; $p<0.01$). Thus, it is indicated that,

hypothesis 1 of the study which stated that, there is no significant relationship between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness is therefore not supported.

Hypothesis 2:

Instructional leadership and teacher empowerment do not contribute towards achieving school effectiveness.

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis of the Contributions of Instructional Leadership and Teacher Empowerment towards Achieving School Effectiveness

Variables	B	S.E	B	t	P
(Constant)	8.714	2.891		3.014	0.03
Instructional Leadership	.562	.051	.515	11.00	.000
Teacher Empowerment	.525	.067	.369	7.881	.000

$R^2 = 0.628$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.625$; $F_{(7,72050)} = 221.819$; $p < .05$

Note: B= Unstandardized Coefficients; S.E= Standard Error; β = Standardized Coefficients.

For the assessment of the contributions of instructional leadership and teacher empowerment in the process of achieving an effective school system, standard multiple regressions were computed in the study. The preliminary assumptions testing for normality, linearity, multi-collinearity and homoscedasticity proved non-violation of the preliminary basic assumptions. In addition, summary of ANOVA results indicated that, regression model is significant ($F=221.819$; $p=0.000$). The regression analysis in Table 2 showed that instructional leadership contributes significantly towards attaining school effectiveness ($\beta=0.515$, $t=11.000$, $p=0.000$); while teacher empowerment contributes significantly towards attaining school effectiveness ($\beta=0.369$, $t=7.881$, $p=0.000$). This therefore proved that, hypothesis 2 of the study which stated that, instructional leadership and teacher empowerment do not contribute towards achieving school effectiveness is therefore not supported.

Discussion of Findings

The data analysed in this study revealed that, there is a significant relationship between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness among public secondary schools in Zamfara State,

Nigeria. In other words, in order to achieve an effective school system, instructional leadership and teacher empowerment should be implemented. Hence, the higher the instructional leadership the higher the school effectiveness. Also, the higher the teacher empowerment, the higher the school effectiveness. This finding is in agreement with that of Yousefi et al. (2021) observed in their study that, there is a high significant relationship between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness. To attain an effective school system instructional leadership and teachers' involvement in all school activities and decision making are the key characteristics. The finding is also in harmony with that of Ismail et al. (2021) who posited that, there is a significant relationship that exists between effective instructional leadership, teacher involvement in school activities (Which was regarded as teachers' empowerment in the present study) and school effectiveness. Ismail et al.'s findings also stressed that, school leaders have to empower and motivate teachers in order to realize the school effectiveness and teachers' work should be recognized and rewarded accordingly. Similarly, Dahiru et al. (2017a) established that, there is a

significant relationship between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness. According to their findings, school effectiveness has been one of the broad critical concepts in education sector and thus entails all the elements of both instructional leadership and teachers' empowerment in a school setting. In addition, Dahiru et al. (2017b) also conducted a study to examine the effective school characteristics as antecedents of teacher empowerment. Results from the study exposed that, there is a significant correlation between school leadership, teacher empowerment and school effectiveness.

Furthermore, the current study observed that, both instructional leadership and teachers' empowerment contribute towards achieving school effectiveness. However, the study observed that, instructional leadership ($\beta=0.515$, $t=11.000$, $p=0.000$) contributes higher than teachers' empowerment ($\beta=0.369$, $t=7.881$, $p=0.000$). The study concluded that, school effectiveness entails a series of activities that include the characteristics of teachers' empowerment and effective school leadership. Zamir (2020) conducted a study on a review of school effectiveness theory for school improvement. The outcomes of Zamir's study revealed that, to achieve school effectiveness there is a need for the implementation of teachers' empowerment and effective leadership in the school system. This finding is also in line with the findings of Mon & Ye (2021) who conducted a study on the relationship between school leadership and teacher empowerment, the findings of their study revealed that, instructional leadership and teachers' empowerment are the conjoined forces that contribute upon the realisation of an effective school system. Kiptum (2018) found in his study that there is a significant relationship between instructional leadership, teacher empowerment towards actualisation of effective school

characteristics. Kiptum further stressed that, in order to improve school effectiveness, focus should be added on the development of qualified and experienced teachers with strong instructional leadership abilities. Danbaba et al. (2021) discovered that, instructional leadership in education entails responsibilities of developing teachers' empowerment, students' academic achievements and involvement of all school participants towards achieving an effective school system. In addition, Akram et al. (2017) observed that, the practices of instructional leadership and their constructs contribute significantly in attaining an effective school system. Instructional leadership also helps in passing judgement on the extent to which school effectiveness is being achieved. In addition, Saleem et al. (2012) posited in their study that, effective leadership and teachers' empowerment with its features are among the key determinants of school effectiveness. Thus, effective school system cannot be fully achieved without the integration of instructional leadership and teachers' empowerment in the daily routines of school proceedings.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to examine the contributions of instructional leadership and teachers' empowerment towards achieving an effective school system. Results obtained from the study expressed that, instructional leadership and teacher empowerment correlates with school effectiveness at high a level of significance. Moreover, instructional leadership and teacher empowerment contributes significantly towards attainment of school effectiveness. These significant correlations therefore, highlighted that, in order to create an effective school system, educational authorities, policy makers, school principals, classroom teachers should cooperate together in the proper implementation and improvement of instructional leadership and teacher empowerment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations have been made:

1. School administrators should keep teachers engaged in all school programs towards achieving an effective school system.
2. School teachers should always support school administrators in all school activities for the purpose of actualisation of an effective school system.

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References

- Akram, M., Kiran, S. & Ilgan, A. (2017). Development and Validation of Instructional Leadership Questionnaire. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 6(17), 73-88.
- Beare, H. (2001). *Creating the future school*. Routledge.
- Bolin, F.S. (1989). Empowering Leadership. *Teachers College Record*, 91(1), 81-96.
- Botha, J. (2011). *The Role of Higher Education Policy in Distance Education Provision in South Africa*. Pretoria: University of South Africa.
- Burusic, J., Babarovic, T. & Velic, M.S. (2016). *School Effectiveness: An Overview of Conceptual, Methodological and Empirical Foundations in School Effectiveness and Educational Management*. Springer International.
- Cochran, W.G. (2007). *Sampling Techniques*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Chhange, R. & Hnamte, L. (2020). Perceptions of Higher Secondary School Teachers of Mizoram on Their Levels of Empowerment on Decision Making and Professional Growth. *Social Science and Humanities Journal*, 4(11), 2031-2035.
- Cotton, K. (2004). Principals and Student Achievement. *What the Research Says*, 88(639), 92-94.
- Crosswell, L. (2006). *Understanding Teacher Commitment in Times of Change*. Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Queensland University of Technology.
- Dahiru, A.S., Pihie, Z.A., Basri, R. & Hassan, S.A. (2017a). Mediating Effect of Teacher Empowerment between Entrepreneurial Leadership and School Effectiveness. *The Social Sciences* 12(11), 2077-2084.
- Dahiru, A.S., Basri, R., & Pihie, Z.A. (2017b). Effective School Characteristics as Antecedents of Teacher Empowerment. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 35(7), 1156-1161. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5829/idosi.wasj.2017.1156.1161>
- Danbaba, A.S., Panshak, T.N. & Ibrahim, M.M. (2021). Educational Leadership Practices in Secondary Schools: The Role of Principals in Goal Achievement. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies*, 3(1), 191 – 200.
- Dinie, D.D., Tirfe, T.M. & Ayenew, W.D. (2017). Factors that Affect Instructional Leadership Role in Improving Students Academic Achievement in Secondary Schools of Ilu Ababor Zone. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 5(10), 1576-1588.
- Federal Government of Nigeria. (2014). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Harris, A. (2011). *Professional Learning Communities in Action*. Leannta Press. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21474/IJAR01/5674>
- Ikegbusi, N.G. & Iheanacho, R.C. (2016). Factors Militating Against Effective Administration of Secondary Schools in

- Anambra State. *World Journal of Educational Research*, 3(1), 1-14.
- Ismail, M., Khatibi, A. A., & Azam, S. M. F. (2021). The moderating role of school level in the relationship between deputy principal's instructional leadership and school effectiveness in public schools in Maldives. *Research in Educational Administration & Leadership*, 6(2), 472-513.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.30828/real/2021.2.4>
- Jafar, S., Audu, A.R., Dahiru, A.S. (2021). Correlate of Workers' Empowerment and Commitment to Duty among Public Secondary School Teachers in Funtua LGA, Katsina State. *Zamfara International Journal of Education*, 1(1), 82-92.
- Khan, I., Hanif, M.H. & Saeed, N. (2020). Instructional Leadership at Government Secondary Schools: An Analytical Study. *Journal of Managerial Sciences*, 14(1), 76-88.
- Kiptum, C. (2018). Correlation between Instructional Leadership and Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Baringo County, Kenya. *British Journal of Education*, 6(1), 92-102.
- Kirk, D. J. & Jones, T. L. (2004). *Effective Schools*. Pearson Education, Inc.
- Lezotte, K.M. & Snyder, K.M. (2011). *What Effective Schools Do: Re-Envisioning the Correlates*. Solution Tree Press.
- Lezotte, L. (1991). *Correlates of Effective Schools: The First and Second Generation*. Effective Schools Products.
- Lima, N.E. (2006). *A Case Study on Principal Behaviors Cultivating a Positive School Culture in an Elementary School*. Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Johnson & Wales University.
- Lucey, T. A. & Hill-Clarke, K. (2008). Considering Teacher Empowerment: Why it is Moral? *Teacher Education & Practice*, 21(1), 47-62.
- Mielcarek, J.A., Hoy, W. & Miskel, C. (2005). *Instructional Leadership: A Learning-Centered Guide*. Information Age Publishers.
- Mon, N.E. & Ye, Y. (2021). A study of the relationship between transformational leadership and teacher empowerment at Daruna Ratchaburi Witaed Suksa School in Ratchaburi Province, Thailand. *Scholar: Human Sciences*, 13(1), 152-163.
- Muhammad, N. & Abid Hussain Chaudharu, A.H. (2020). Relationship of Teachers' Empowerment and Organizational Commitment at Secondary School Level in Punjab. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 42(2), 69-80.
- Muhammad, N. (2014). *Perception of Teachers and Head Teachers about Organizational Politics at Secondary Level*. Unpublished M.Phil Dissertation, University of Education.
- Murphy, J. (1988). Methodological, Measurement, and Conceptual Problems in the Study of Instructional Leadership. *Educational Evaluation & Policy Analysis*, 10(2), 117-139.
- Olorunfemi, D.O. (2008). Challenges of Instructional Supervision in the New Millennium: Implication for Effective Planning. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(2), 68- 80.
- Oyedeji, N.B. (2012). *Supervision and Standard of Education in Nigerian Secondary Schools*. Unpublished manuscript, University of Ilorin.
- Rossouw, L. F. (1990). *The Principalship: Dimensions in Instructional Leadership*. Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Saleem, F., Naseem, Z., Ibrahim, K., Hussain, A. & Azeem, M. (2012). Determinants of School Effectiveness: A study at Punjab level. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(14), 242-251.
- Scheerens, J. (2000). *Improving School Effectiveness*. United Nations

- Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- Scheerens, J. (2004). *Review of School and Instructional Effectiveness Research*. Educational for All Global Monitoring Report. <https://ris.utwente.nl>
- Sharp, D.C. (2009). *A Study of the Relationship between Teacher Empowerment and Principal Effectiveness*. [Unpublished PhD Dissertation] Baker University.
- Short, P. M. (1994). Defining Teacher Empowerment. *Education Electronic Version*, 114, 488-493.
- Short, P. M., & J. S. Rinehart. (1992). School participant empowerment scale: Assessment of level of empowerment within the school environment. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 52(4), 951-960.
- Sparks, D. (2003). Change Agent: An Interview with Michael Fullan. *Journal of Staff Development*, 24(1), 55–58.
- Squire-Kelly, V. D. (2012). *The Relationship between Teacher Empowerment and Student Achievement*. Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Georgia Southern University.
- Tan, C. Y. (2012). Instructional leadership: Toward a Contextualized Knowledge Creation Model. *School Leadership & Management*, 32(2), 183–194.
- Yousefi, A., Zahed, A.B. & Kia, M.M. (2021). The Relationship between Principals' Instructional Leadership and School Effectiveness with the Mediating Role of School Culture in Ardabil Province's Secondary Schools. *Journal of Research and Urban Planning*, 12(2), 76-92.
- Zamfara State Government. (2021). *The Government Owned Secondary Schools and their Total Number of in-service Teachers*. Unpublished Official Document, Zamfara State Ministry of Education.
- Zamir, N. A. (2020). A Review of School Effectiveness Theory for School Improvement. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(3), 113–101.